

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

STATISTICAL MODELING AND FORECASTING BANK DEPOSIT DATA USING RANDOM FORESTS

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ABSTRACT

In the field of financial and foreign exchange markets, large amounts of data of various nature are accumulated. Extracting essential information from this data aiming to provide a base for taking proper management decisions of the banks executive boards, companies and other financial institutions is an important practical task. The process of solving problems related to the processing of financial data in the era of ubiquitous digitalization is increasingly achieved with the application of the most modern and powerful mathematical tools and the techniques and algorithms developed on their basis. The purpose of this study is to analyze and forecast real data from the currency deposits of Bulgarian citizens. The data are in the form of a univariate time series on a monthly basis. They are modeled using the powerful Random forests (RF) machine learning method. Predictive RF models were created and tested, achieving up to 98% data matching. The models are applied to short-term forecasts, simulating the prediction of future deposit values.

Keywords: univariate time series, machine learning, predictive model, random forests, classification and regression trees (CART).

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent decade, the central banks' quantitative easing policies implemented to stimulate growth in the world's leading economies generated big excess of money worldwide. The financial world found itself in a situation where for several years the banks had to apply zero or negative interest rates on their deposit products.

The recent geopolitical changes led to a normalization of market conditions and practically the banks began again to reward their depositors for keeping their money, rather than penalizing them for owning it. This led to a revival of interest in the bank deposit, which once again became an instrument of profitability for bank depositors.

In fact, the bank deposit is a product offered by banks all over the world, widely used since the appearance of the money as a payment tool. This is because this instrument combines security, clear profitability and an almost complete guarantee for the invested money, even in case of bank failure. From one hand when the individual investor make investment in a bank deposit in a foreign currency, he protects his own savings from local inflationary processes, protects both, the nominal and the purchase value of his money and almost covers the full range of risks related to his own country - political, economic and internal crisis. From other hand, for the banks, the bank deposit is a safe instrument for attracting fresh money, with which they can operate in a short and medium term, under clear rules, structure and preliminary agreed fixed conditions. Undoubtedly, the bank deposit is a win-win process, and in the financial world, the good deals are those where all parties involved are happy with the outcome.

Modeling financial data in the form of time series is a challenging task. This stems from their complex

volatile nature, involving non-linear interrelationships both between the data within the time series itself and stochastic influence from external, often unspecified variable factors.

The aim of this study is to process, analyze and forecast real data from the bank currency deposits of Bulgarian citizens. To achieve this goal, the performance of the powerful ensemble learning method Random Forests (RF) is investigated. The obtained models are intended for short-term forecasts of the studied time series.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

To discover this type of dependencies, modern machine learning (ML) methods and algorithms deliver reliable and powerful tools for processing, analyzing and forecasting of financial data. The core methods used for this are: Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Support vector regression (SVR), Classification and regression trees (CART), RF, Naïve Bayes (NB), Multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS), and more.

In recent years, a number of scientific publications present a variety of ML approaches and models for processing financial and currency data. The authors of review article [1] used a novel dataset from the Netherlands' banking sector, to examine how macroeconomic, bank-specific, and account-specific characteristics affect the interest rates of banking products. Time deposits have been shown to reflect the economic environment of banks more accurately than bank interest rates on savings accounts. Paper [2] provides unique empirical evidence regarding the determinants of deposit pricing by employing Generalized linear models, MARS, SVR, ANN, CART, and RF. In [3] a new strategy is presented based on two data mining algorithms one of which is RF. It is concluded that algorithmic trading

based on combination of classification and Probit regression can be effective in improving the prediction accuracy. The authors of [4] presents a customer-specific interest rate determination system for a bank’s time deposit products from Turkey using ML algorithms. A large-scale comparison for the major machine learning models for time series forecasting is presented in [5].

In [6] a large amount of Portuguese retail bank data is used to predict whether a new customer plans to have a term deposit or not. The authors compare the performance of the three classification algorithms: Support Vector Machine (SVM), Neural Network (NN), and NB. The best results are obtained by the NB models. Paper [7] investigates bank customers' intention to use or not use a bank time deposit service. For this purpose, data on 21 influencing factors are analyzed. Base ML models with gradient boosting decision tree (GBDT), extreme gradient boosting (Xgboost), and distributed gradient lifting framework (LightGBM) are built and tested. The three base models are then stacked using logistic regression (LR). Predictive models with CART Ensembles and Bagging and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) of one-dimensional time series with bank deposits are built and analyzed in [8]. Accuracy of the models to by over 93% match with the data was achieved. The authors of [9] apply NB and K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN) to classify bank customer deposit data. More accurate results were

obtained with K-NN, reaching 89% correct classification. Another aspect explored with ML in the field of bank deposits is bank telemarketing for selling long-term deposits. Among the few publications on this topic, we will mention [10], where four methods are used for classification: multilayer perceptron neural network (MLPNN), decision tree (C4.5), logistic regression and RF. The results show that RF achieves the highest accuracy of 87% in terms of prediction ability. The RF classifier also showed the best classification accuracy of 86.8%, as well as 92.7% for receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC) evaluation.

3. DATA AND METHODS

3.1.Data description

In this study, we examine monthly data on deposits of Bulgarian citizens in US dollars. The research covers the period from February 2004 to December 2022, total N=227 cases, in millions of dollars. The data are extracted from the official website of the Bulgarian National Bank [11]. We denote the variable of the formed time series by *Depos227*. Figure 1 shows its sequence chart. The weak linear decreasing trend is displayed by the equation:

$$Y = -0.8773t + 248.77 \tag{1}$$

where *t* is a time indicator. Equation (1) explains the global linear tendency of the data with about R²=26.6%.

Figure 1. Sequence plot of the examined dataset of deposits (*Depos227*).

Table 1 shows the main statistical indicators of the variable *Depos227*. From the relatively large values of skewness and kurtosis we can conclude that the data do not have a normal distribution. This can be also seen from the corresponding histogram and boxplot of the distribution illustrated in Figure 2.

Table 1.

Descriptive statistics of the *Depos227*.

Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Std. Err. of Skewness	Kurtosis	Std. Err. of Kurtosis	Minimum	Maximum
148.76	128.08	111.76	1.050	0.162	1.072	0.322	1.20	543.73

Figure 2. Histogram and boxplot of the distribution of Depos227.

Since the data are not normally distributed, the use of classical parametric methods such as multiple linear regression, ARIMA and others is not recommended. In our case, we will use RF, which has no restrictions on the distribution of variables.

1.1. Brief description of Random Forests

The Random Forests (RF) method was proposed by Leo Breiman [12]. It does not depend on the type of data's distribution, it works with numerical and nominal data, it is applicable to multiclass classification and regression problems, it models high-dimensional tasks and it can be parallelized.

RF generates hundreds of independent classification and regression trees (CART) [13, 14]. The initial sample of original data is randomly divided into two parts. The first part called Out_Of_Bag (OOB), consisting about 1/3 of the whole data is set aside for testing and does not participate in the modeling procedure. The second part consisting the remaining 2/3 of the data is used to form bootstrap samples (by randomly sampling with replacement) necessary to fill up to the full size of the original data. With each bootstrap sample, a tree is built according to preliminary set RF hyper parameters, without additional training (so-called maximum trees). The resulting model is validated on the OOB test sample. The full information regarding the summary statistics of the test model with OOB is provided. The final

RF model is the arithmetic mean of the predictions of the single trees. The best model should be the model that optimizes the OOB statistics. RF provides additional functions for weighting and relative weighting of the predictors used in a regression model, differential weights in multiclass classification, filling of missing values, error visualization and so on.

The RF hyper parameters are: number of trees (Mtree), minimum observations in a terminal node of the tree (Atm, atoms), number of predictors randomly selected from the total number of predictors (Mtry) separately for each split of each node of each RF tree, etc. By default, Mtry=3, proposed and proved in [12].

In this study we implement the RF Tree Ensembles algorithm from Salford Predictive Modeler software [15].

1.2. Statistical measures for model accuracy evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the constructed models the following standard statistical measures are used: mean square error (MSE), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), and coefficient of determination (R^2), determined by the expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MSE} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N (P_t - Y_t)^2, & \text{RMSE} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N (P_t - Y_t)^2}, \\ \text{MAPE} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left| \frac{P_t - Y_t}{Y_t} \right|, & R^2 &= 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (P_t - Y_t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^N (Y_t - \bar{Y})^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In (2) Y_t and P_t are the values of the dependent variable Y and predicted variable P , respectively, \bar{Y} is the mean value of Y , N is the sample size. The predictive model is good, when R^2 is close to 1 and

the errors RMSE and MAPE are small. We will also check the adequacy of the built models by means of the ACF of residuals based on the Ljung-Box portfolio test [16,17].

2. RESULTS

Time series modeling usually aims to predict future values. For this purpose, the initial dataset is divided into two parts – learning and test subsamples, where the test sample includes some of the last values of the time series. The models are built and trained on the learning subset, and the accuracy of their prediction is verified with the test sample. In our case, the first N1=224 data are used for the learning sample, labeled $Y=Depos224$, and the last 3 values are set aside for the test sample.

$$Trend_t = Y_t - Y_{t-1}, t = 2, 3, \dots, 224, Trend_1 = Trend_2 \tag{3}$$

The values of the lagged variables are respectively lagged by k lags relative to the current time t:

$$Depos224 < k >_t = Y_{t-k}, t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 224 + k, \tag{4}$$

and the first missing values are filled with Y_1 .

Multiple models were built varying the set of predictors. The hyper parameters were set as follows:

- Mtree = 500, 700, and 1000; Atm = 2, 5, 10, and 20; Mtry=3.

The models were trained with the standard OOB test sample described above in Section 3.2. As an illus-

In order to build the model independent time series (features or predictors) are needed. Initially, we only have the *Depos227* data, i.e. we have univariate time series and we have no predictors. Following our previous experience from [8], in this study we will use the following time series as predictors: trend and several lagged variables *Depos224<1>*, *Depos224<2>*, ..., *Depos224<6>*. We calculate the trend using the first order finite difference formulae:

tration of the selection depending on the hyper-parameter Atm, Figure 3 and Table 2 show the statistics of the four models with Mtree=1000 and predictors *Trend*, *Depos224<1>*, *Depos224<2>*, *Depos224<6>*. In this example, it is found that model C2 with Atm=5 (minimum cases in terminal node) has the best statistics compared to all four statistical indicators from (2).

Figure 3. Example of the obtained values of MSE for four RF models of Depos224 for different values (atoms) of the hyper-parameter Atm.

Table 2 presents the statistics (2) for the OOB samples of exemplary models C1, C2, C3 and C4, generated for Atm=2,5,10, and 20, respectively.

Table 2.

OOB statistics of the four exemplary models for different Atm values.

Model	Mtree	Atm	MSE	RMSE	MAPE	R ²
C1	1000	2	1652.417	40.650	0.525	0.868
C2	1000	5	1563.560	39.542	0.392	0.876
C3	1000	10	1889.660	43.470	0.429	0.849
C4	1000	20	2473.202	49.731	0.536	0.803

The best training and prediction results were obtained with the following hyper parameters: Mtree = 1000, Atm = 5, Mtry=3. The final statistics of three best predicting RF models selected by measures (2) for OOB and comparison with the dependent variable *Depos224* are given in Table 3. Lowest errors and highest R²=98.4% were achieved with RFModel 2. It is generated with the variables *Trend*, the first two lagged

variables *Depos224<1>* and *<2>*. It is followed by the RFModel 3, in which *Depos224<6>* is also involved. According to the well-known Lewis's scale [18] with a MAPE value between 11 and 20%, the RFModel 2 model can be characterized as a model with "good forecast accuracy".

Table 3.

Statistics of the best predictive RF models of Depos224.

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAPE	R ²	Predictors
RFModel 1	507.546	22.529	0.253	0.972	Trend, Depos224<1>, <2>, <3>, <6>
RFModel 2	281.469	16.777	0.175	0.984	Trend, Depos224<1>, <2>
RFModel 3	385.535	19.635	0.219	0.978	Trend, Depos224<1>, <2>, <6>

The following Table 4 gives the relative weights of the predictors in the three selected best models. For all three cases, the highest weight of score 100 is for *Trend*, followed by *Depos224<1>*. In the last column of Table 4 are the model forecasts for the test 3 months, whose data were not used in the modeling process. The

real values of deposits are consecutively (80.0, 79.4, 170.4). RFModel 3 has the smallest deviations here, but the spike in the last month is better predicted by RFModel 2.

In conclusion, we should choose the second model as the best one.

Table 4.

Relative variable importance and forecasted values of the best RF models.

Model	Trend	Depos224<1>	<2>	<3>	<6>	Forecasts 3 months
RFModel 1	100	71.3	4.7	5.8	2.6	(85.4, 124.5, 118.7)
RFModel 2	100	92.6	3.7	-	-	(83.6, 137.6, 148.3)
RFModel 3	100	81.8	6.0	-	2.5	(84.5, 121.8, 134.1)

Figure 4 shows the RFModel 2 approximation to the entire *Depos227* time series. A very good match is observed, except for some peak values. This phenomenon is characteristic of RF and other ensemble meth-

ods, as they calculate their approximations by averaging the predictions of many trees. Figure 5 presents a scatter plot of the actual versus RFModel 2 predicted deposit values with a 95% confidence interval.

Figure 4. Comparison of initial time series deposit data with predictions from RFModel 2.

Figure 5. Observed vs. Predicted by model RFModel 2 deposit values with 95% confidence interval.

4.2. Analysis of model residuals

We need verify the adequacy of the selected best model RFModel 2 by diagnosing and analyzing its residuals. For this purpose, we construct the ACF plot of the residuals for the last 24 months. It is shown in Figure 6. All residuals are within the confidence limits.

Figure 6. Observed vs. Predicted by model RFModel 2 deposit values with 95% confidence interval.

From these results, we can conclude that the selected best RF model RFModel 2 is adequate and the obtained predictions can be accepted.

DISCUSSION WITH CONCLUSION

This paper develops a novel approach to modeling and forecasting the univariate time series by the financial sector. The empirical study uses bank data on short-term deposits of Bulgarian citizens denoted with the variable *Depos227*. Based on the statistical indicators we concluded that the data do not have a normal distribution. In such assumptions, the application of standard classical multivariate statistical methods, such as multiple linear regression, ARIMA, and others is difficult and often leads to inaccurate results. For this reason, we chose to implement the powerful ML method Random Forests, which is distribution free and is not affected by possible multicollinearity of predictor variables. To build predictive models, we constructed predictors based on the characteristics of the studied time series – first order trend and several of its lagged variables. Multiple models were built varying the set of predictors. The models were trained with the standard OOB test sample and it is found that models with 1000 trees and $Atm=5$ (minimum cases in terminal node) have the best statistical measures. Lowest errors and highest coefficient of determination $R^2=98.4\%$ were achieved with RFModel 2. It is generated with the variables *Trend*, the first two lagged variables *Depos224<1>* and *<2>*. After analysis of the models residuals we concluded that selected best RF model RFModel 2 is adequate and the obtained predictions can be accepted. What is new in our approach is the inclusion of trend and lagged variables as predictors.

In common, the proposed approach with the use of the RF algorithm demonstrates promising capabilities for modeling, analyzing and forecasting the univariate time series for financial data of stochastic nature.

Therefore, we can assume that there is no autocorrelation in them. Ljung-Box test [16] residual statistics were additionally calculated. All of them are insignificant and therefore, the residual underlying process assumed is independent (white noise).

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